
**STUDY OF AXISYMMETRIC ROTATING
DIFFERENTIALLY HEATED ANNULAR CAVITY VIA A
SPECTRAL ITERATIVE DOMAIN DECOMPOSITION
TECHNIQUE. PRELIMINARY RESULTS**

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Abstract

Computation of Chebyshev spectral analysis approximation has been developed in order to solve coupling of Navier-Stokes and heat equations for a differentially heated annular cavity under axisymmetric conditions. A domain decomposition technique introduced by Hugues and Randriamampianina in [4] has been used to solve coupling between pressure and velocity in N-S equations. A detailed description of the solution method is provided in this paper. Preliminary results are presented for temperature field and stability of the system under two different heat transport regimes: conduction and advection. This

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paper attempts to describe fundamentals for further investigations that are being developed for this system in axisymmetric and three-dimensional conditions.

1. Introduction

Understanding atmosphere and ocean dynamics requires a precise knowledge of the forcing factors involved in the system such as gravity, earth rotation and differential heating. However, the complexity of the system makes several simplifications necessary when studying the system in laboratory experiments or via numerical simulations. One of the best-known simplifications is the baroclinic annular differentially heated cavity, a representation of which is given in Figure 1.

This simplification entails transforming spherical coordinates to cylindrical coordinates, which considerably reduces the mathematical difficulties of obtaining numerical solutions to the equations. It also proves helpful when carrying out the laboratory experiment. Approximation is mainly valid for middle-north latitude when vector \vec{g} might be considered downwards.

The annular cavity is termed baroclinic because the pressure and density lines are not parallel. Such phenomena are observed in oceans and the troposphere and are fundamentally due to the effect of temperature variation on density. In this paper, the Boussinesq approximation is considered to describe density variation, taking temperature $\rho(T)$ as a lineal function:

$$\rho(T) = \rho_0(1 - \alpha(T - T_0)), \quad (1.1)$$

where ρ_0 represents mean density, α thermal cubic expansion, and T_0 is the average temperature between the annulus walls.

The preliminary results presented in this paper have been obtained for axisymmetric conditions. According to the theory of axisymmetric flow proposed by Hide [2], differentially heated annular rotating cavity flow can be considered to be axisymmetric if the thermal Rossby number θ has a value of more than 1.58 [2]:

$$\theta = \frac{gs\alpha\Delta T}{\Omega^2(b-a)^2} > \theta_0 \equiv 1.58, \quad (1.2)$$

where g represents the acceleration of gravity, s the annulus height, ΔT the temperature variation between the walls, Ω the angular velocity and $(b-a)$ the width or difference between the outer and inner radii. Phenomena related to axisymmetric flow exist in nature such as tropical wind circulation.

The advection degree of the system has been examined by means of the Péclet number:

$$X = \frac{gs\alpha\Delta T\sqrt{v}}{8k\Omega^{3/2}}, \quad (1.3)$$

where k represents the thermal diffusivity and v is the kinematic viscosity. When $X > 1$, advection dominates the system whereas if $X < 1$, thermal diffusivity controls heat transfer [3]. A simulation has been developed of each of these two situations.

Figure 1. Representation of annular cavity (a) and comparison with earth system (b). Approximation is mainly valid in the middle-north latitude while vector \vec{g} might be considered vertical and downwards, Elliot [1].

2. Equations of the Problem

The cylindrical coordinates system of reference centered on the rotational axis is used. Vector velocity is given by the Navier-Stokes equation (2.1) where the Boussinesq approximation (1.1) is considered for

the sake of simplicity, solely in terms of gravity and centrifugal acceleration. The heat equation (2.2) describes the temperature evolution of the system. Fluid incompressibility is also considered in (2.3):

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{v} + 2\Omega \hat{k} \times \vec{v} = -\vec{\nabla}p + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v} + \vec{F}, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla})T = k \nabla^2 T, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} = 0, \quad (2.3)$$

where \vec{v} describes velocity, Ω angular velocity, ν kinematic viscosity and T is the temperature. \vec{F} represents the external forces affected by the Boussinesq approximation, in such a way that it is temperature-dependent. Finally, p is the reduced pressure:

$$F = \alpha(T - T_0)(g\hat{k} - r\Omega^2\hat{r}), \quad (2.4)$$

$$p = \frac{P}{\rho_0} + gz - \frac{(r\Omega)^2}{2}. \quad (2.5)$$

These equations have been adimensionalized. The reference parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Reference parameters for adimensionalization. Dimensionless numbers used are: Taylor number (Ta), Prandtl number (Pr), Rayleigh number (Ra), Froude number (Fr) and thermal Rossby number (θ). Aspect ratio is defined by A

$A = \frac{s}{b-a}$	$\nu_{ref} = \frac{g\alpha\Delta T}{2\Omega}$	$Ra = \frac{g\alpha\Delta T(b-a)^3}{\nu k}$
$r_{ref} = \frac{rh}{2}$	$p_{ref} = \frac{1}{2}\rho_0 g\alpha\Delta Ts$	$Pr = \frac{\nu}{k}$
$s_{ref} = \frac{s}{2}$	$T_{ref} = \frac{\Delta T}{2}$	$Ta = \frac{4\Omega^2(b-a)^5}{\nu^2 s}$
$t_{ref} = \frac{1}{2\Omega}$	$\theta = \frac{gs\alpha\Delta T}{\Omega^2(b-a)^2}$	$Fr = \frac{\Omega^2(b-a)}{g}$

3. Solution of the Equations

Transformation of the resolution space

A multidomain parallel spectral computing technique has been used to solve the problem. In particular, Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto collocation points have been chosen to approximate the solutions via Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, thus requiring transformation of the resolution space in order to use Chebyshev functions, which are defined in $[-1, 1]$ domain.

There have been defined np subdomains for the radial coordinate of size: $rh = \frac{b-a}{np}$. On the other hand, no subdomains decomposition for axial coordinate has been taken. As Chebyshev polynomials are defined into $[-1, +1]$, transform equations yield to be:

$$r' = \frac{2}{rh} \cdot r - r_i, \quad (3.1)$$

$$z' = \frac{2}{d} \cdot z - 1, \quad (3.2)$$

where i denotes each domain and $r_i = \frac{2a + (2i+1)rh}{rh}$ is the local curvature parameter.

Spatial approximation in spectral space

Any variable is approximated at each domain according to the formula shown as:

$$f_{NM}(t, r, z) = \sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{m=0}^M f_{nm}(t) T_m\left(\frac{2r}{A-1}\right) T_n(2z-1), \quad (3.3)$$

where T_m and T_n represent the Chebyshev polynomials of maximum degrees M and N , respectively. Therefore, solutions are calculated over an $M \times N$ grid in spectral space, which corresponds to an axisymmetric r - Z

plane in physical space*. The Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto collocation points are defined over its domain in such a way that most of the points are close to the boundaries. Consequently, an accuracy is expected to be greater along the walls than in the middle of the annular cavity for all the variables $f = (u, v, w, p, T)$.

Temporal discretization and projection scheme

Temporal approximation is based on a combination of the Adams-Bashforth method and backward differentiation formula. Equations (2.1) and (2.2) become:

$$\frac{3\bar{v}^{n+1} + 4\bar{v}^n + \bar{v}^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} + 2N(\bar{v}^n) - N(\bar{v}^{n-1}) = -\bar{\nabla}p^{n+1} + \nu\nabla^2\bar{v}^{n+1} + \bar{F}^n, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial T^{n+1} - 4T^n + T^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} + 2N(T^n) - N(T^{n-1}) = k\nabla^2 T^{n+1}, \quad (3.5)$$

where $N(\bar{v})$ and $N(T)$ denote non-linear terms and Δt is the time step interval. Unknown terms are designated by index $n + 1$ whereas terms over n and $n - 1$ are known previous iteration quantities. It should be noted that the external forces (where Coriolis iteration is included) are known in this equation. At the initial step, it is taken to be $f^{-1} = f^0$ for all variables.

Equation (3.5) is an easily solved Helmholtz equation for temperature. On the other hand, as pressure is considered unknown in equation (3.4), the coupling between pressure and velocity in this equation is solved by the projection scheme decomposition method. This method, which was introduced by Hugues and Randriamampianina in [4] and finally developed by Louchart et al. [5] one year later, basically entails first calculating a pressure predictor that is then used to solve vector-velocity in Navier-Stokes equations. Assuming incompressibility conditions (2.3) and taking the divergence of equation (3.4), it becomes:

$$\Delta p^* = -\bar{\nabla} \cdot (2N(\bar{v}^n)) - N(\bar{v}^{n-1}) + \bar{\nabla} \cdot \bar{F}^n. \quad (3.6)$$

*Degree of Chebyshev polynomials used in the code: $M = 49$, $N = 64$.

The above is an easily solved Poisson equation for pressure. The resultant quantity can be used to solve velocity in equation (3.4), which becomes a Helmholtz equation once the pressure is known:

$$\frac{3\bar{v}^{n+1} + 4\bar{v}^n + \bar{v}^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} + 2N(\bar{v}^n) - N(\bar{v}^{n-1}) = -\bar{\nabla}p^* + \nu\nabla^2\bar{v}^{n+1} + \bar{F}^n. \quad (3.7)$$

Lastly, a correction step is needed to update velocity and pressure from these preliminary values, all the details of which can be found in references [4-6]. This semi-implicit iterative method enables calculation of every time step velocity, pressure and temperature. It should be noted that the temperature in previous time step n affects the external forces term \bar{F}^n (Boussinesq approximation) in the momentum equation.

Boundary conditions

No-slip boundary conditions are assumed for velocity throughout the annular cavity. Temperature is considered constant but different over the walls of the cylinder cavity (the outer wall is warmer) while adiabatic conditions are assumed for the top and bottom bases. The cylinder top base is free. In short:

$$z = 0 : u = v = w = 0; \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0,$$

$$z = s : \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = 0; w = 0; \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0,$$

$$r = a : u = v = w = 0; T = -1,$$

$$r = b : u = v = w = 0; T = +1.$$

4. Results

Preliminary results have been obtained to reach a first approximation of the validity of this method for the resolution of temperature field over a heated rotating annular cavity. Two simulations in axisymmetric conditions (thermal Rossby number: $\theta = 2.43$) have been developed in order to

compare these results with an analytical model: Hide [2]. A summary of the parameters used in the code is given in Table 2.[†]

Table 2. Parameters used in the code. Cubic thermal expansion α , angular velocity Ω , kinematic viscosity ν , mean density ρ_0 , inner radius a , outer radius b , height s , and temperature variance between walls ΔT . Two values for thermal diffusivity - k_a and k_c - have been used in order to compare advection and conduction regimes, respectively

$g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}$	$\alpha = 4.5 \text{ cm}$
$\Omega = 0.4 \text{ rd/s}$	$b = 12 \text{ cm}$
$\Delta T = 7.98^\circ \text{C}$	$s = 13.5 \text{ cm}$
$\rho_0 = 998.21 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$	$A = 1.8$
$\nu = 1.004\cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	$k_a = 1.434\cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$
$\alpha = 0.207\cdot 10^{-3} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$k_c = 0.01 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

Simulations have been developed with four processors ($np = 4$) so that all the equations are solved in four domains along the radius. The time step used in the code for temporal data acquisition was $\Delta t = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}$, throughout $N = 10^6$ iterations, thus giving an experiment time of $T = 1250 \text{ s} = 20 \text{ min } 50 \text{ sec}$.

Two different thermal diffusivity values - k_a and k_c - have been used in order to obtain results in advection and convection regimes, respectively. For $k_a = 1.434 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, an advection regime is grown ($X = 55.9 \gg 1$) while for thermal diffusivity $k_c = 0.01 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ heat conduction controls the system ($X = 8.02 \times 10^{-4} \ll 1$). Figure 2 shows the preliminary results obtained for temperature field under these two conditions. As can be

[†]The parameters used in the code are for water, except $k_c = 0.01 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, for which the value was deliberately chosen so high in order to obtain conductive heat transfer conditions.

observed, these results concur with the representation of temperature field reported by Hide [3].

Figure 2. Temperature field. Advection (right) has been obtained for water: $k_a = 1.434 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Conduction regime (left) has been obtained for a fluid with thermal diffusivity coefficient: $k_c = 0.01 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Results are normalized according to: $[T_a, T_b] = [-1, +1]$, $[a, b] = [0, 1]$ and $[0, s] = [0, A]$.

Figure 3. Evolution of temperature at point: (0.892, 1.536), “top left-hand corner” over Figure 2. As expected, the conduction regime (left) reached stability much earlier than the advection regime (right) because mass transfer continues in progress. Note that temperature at this point is higher for advection than conduction.

Temporal stability has been studied via evolution of the temperature at one point of the annular cavity. The results are presented in Figure 3 and it is shown that stability is reached prior to the conduction conditions.

5. Conclusions and Future Guidelines

Temperature field representation has been found to concur very satisfactorily with the Hide theoretical model [3]. As a result, the domain decomposition technique can be considered a successful method for solving Navier-Stokes and heat transfer equations for annular cavity. These preliminary results have been obtained using only four processors. Accuracy is expected to increase on using a larger number of processors.

In this paper, external forces have been considered to be known for the purpose of calculating the vector velocity at each time step (\vec{F}^n). One easy improvement for the next version of the code would be to include velocity terms involved in external forces as an unknown variable in temporal integration (\vec{F}^{n+1}). A more challenging improvement would be to extend this code to three dimensions, which would enable study of the temperature field under non-axisymmetric conditions and even on the azimuthal plane.

There is ample evidence that multi-domain spectral analysis is a powerful tool that yields accurate approximations to dynamic problems. Developing this code might provide an effective instrument to study the characteristics of inertial gravity waves inside a differentially heated annular cavity.

This tool already enables study of important quasi-axisymmetric physical systems such as flow circulation in the troposphere and oceans in the high-north latitude by using an appropriate annulus length and all the approximations mentioned above.

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